

Kinetics and mechanism of CO₂ methanation on a nickel catalyst

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Use has been made of a perfectly stirred catalytic reactor to determine the kinetic data of CO₂ methanation of Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst; the data are analyzed by Hougen-Watson method. The optimal values of kinetic parameters are calculated by means of four kinetic models. Application of Boudart criteria has led to the conclusion that the process occurs according to a Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism with an activation energy of 57.4 kJ mol⁻¹.

The catalytic hydrogenation of carbon dioxide to methane referred to as Sabatier reaction has become a process of major importance in several fields of which an important one is the ammonia industry. The synthesis gas still contains about 0.1% CO₂ and 0.2–0.6% CO after removal of carbon dioxide. However, the process of ammonia synthesis requires less than 10 ppm of oxygen compounds because they represent a strong poison for iron (synthesis) catalyst. Therefore, the removal of carbon oxides from the synthesis gas is compulsory and it is more efficiently achieved by means of methanation catalytic process. In this process the activity of nickel catalyst is rather high, the price acceptable and the selectivity high¹, besides carbon or liquid hydrocarbons are formed only at temperatures exceeding 673 K. Its activation is facile, with process gas. The overall reduction process is weakly exothermic and therefore temperature does not exceed the maximum allowed 723 K; at 773 K thermal deactivation by sintering is reached. The deactivation may also be due to the poisoning of the catalyst. The main poisons, which most frequently originate in the carbon dioxide washing solutions, are sulfur and arsenic compounds. In normal operation conditions the catalyst lifetime may exceed five years.

The actual unfolding of methanation process, as it occurs in ammonia industry, has scarcely been studied². However, kinetic data are available on methanation of carbon monoxide (in absence of dioxide)³ and (fewer) on the methanation of carbon dioxide in absence of monoxide⁴. The literature shows that whenever both the oxides are present in the reaction mixture, the carbon dioxide methanation reaction occurs after methanation of carbon monoxide. The activation energies of the two reactions take close values, that of carbon monoxide methanation being lower.

Quach and Rouleau⁵ investigated the kinetics of carbon dioxide methanation reaction on ruthenium catalyst (cylindrical alumina tablets, 3.2 mm in diameter and thickness,

impregnated with 0.5% ruthenium) in a continuous perfectly stirred reactor, under isothermal conditions, at atmospheric pressure and temperatures in the range 473–573 K.

In this contribution the kinetics of the same process is determined in the case of an industrial nickel on alumina methanation catalyst making use of a perfectly stirred catalytic reactor⁶.

Reaction mechanisms and possible kinetic models :

Reaction mechanisms have been imagined for the heterogeneous catalytic reaction between molecules of the same kind or different molecules; on the basis of these mechanisms kinetic models of the process were developed by various authors⁷.

Boreskov⁸ showed that for a heterogeneous catalytic process the equation of reaction rate should satisfy the general scheme,

$$\text{Reaction rate} = \frac{(\text{kinetic factor})(\text{driving force})}{(\text{resistant factor})^n}$$

which takes account of the mechanism advanced for the process, the rate-determining step, and the reaction regression factors. The general model of writing the reaction rate equation advanced by Boreskov fits Langmuir-Hinshelwood theory of surface reactions.

Langmuir-Hinshelwood's theory⁹ is one of the most frequently employed kinetic theories of heterogeneous catalysis. It supplies hypotheses upon the state (adsorbed or in gas phase) of the reactants and products during the advancement of the reaction. Then one has to check if the experimental data fit the mathematical equations of reaction rate resulted from the assumption of a process mechanism. As for example, if molecules A and B are involved in the reaction and, according to Langmuir-Hinshelwood model, A and B are assumed to react in adsorbed state, the rate of heterogeneous catalytic reaction is

$$r = \frac{kK_A K_B p_A p_B}{(1 + K_A p_A + K_B p_B)^2} \quad (1)$$

where k stands for the kinetic constant of the process, K_A and K_B are the adsorption equilibrium thermodynamic constants of reactants A and B, respectively, and p_A and p_B the partial pressures of the same reactants.

If the reasoning is extended to a gas species, j , the adsorption equilibrium constant K_j is the ratio of the adsorption rate constant k_{ja} , over the desorption one, k_{jd} ; K_j is strictly positive and given by the equation,

$$K_j = \exp \left[-\frac{\Delta G_j^0}{RT} \right] = \exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_j^0}{R} \right] \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{\Delta H_j^0}{RT} \right] \quad (2)$$

where ΔG_j^0 , ΔS_j^0 and ΔH_j^0 stand for the variations of standard free energy, adsorption standard entropy and standard enthalpy, respectively; $R = 8.31 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ the universal gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

Another theory, widely employed in heterogeneous catalysis, was developed by Rideal-Eley¹⁰. They assumed that at the time of reaction, only one of the reactants lies in adsorbed state, while the other one is in gaseous state.

Hougen and Watson extended Langmuir-Hinshelwood and Rideal-Eley models to heterogeneous catalytic reactions: the reacting gases and reaction products can or can not be regarded in adsorbed state; analysis of kinetic data is referred to as Hougen-Watson method¹¹. It is frequently applied in heterogeneous catalysis studies¹², a field which requires mentioning of Rouleau's contribution¹³.

Numerous Hougen-Watson type rate equations can be advanced for carbon dioxide methanation starting up with any combination of adsorbed species (carbon dioxide, hydrogen, methane and water) possibly existing on catalyst surface. Based on thermodynamic data one can disregard the inverse reaction over the whole temperature range of measurements. Desorption could not be a rate-determining step because of the same reason. In spite of these limitations one can write 28 equations of the process rate. From these equations only four fit the models which consider the surface reaction between the adsorbed species as rate-determining step; these models will be adopted as most adequate in describing the real mechanism of the process. They are as follows:

where L stands for an active center on catalyst surface. Four Hougen-Watson type equations of reaction rate correspond to the four possible mechanisms,

$$r = \frac{kK_1 K_2^4 p_1 p_2^4}{(1 + K_1 p_1 + K_2 p_2)^5} \quad (\text{E I})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1 K_2^4 p_1 p_2^4}{(1 + K_1 p_1 + K_2 p_2 + K_3 p_3)^5} \quad (\text{E II})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1 K_2^4 p_1 p_2^4}{(1 + K_1 p_1 + K_2 p_2 + K_4 p_4)^5} \quad (\text{E III})$$

$$r = \frac{kK_1 K_2^4 p_1 p_2^4}{(1 + K_1 p_1 + K_2 p_2 + K_3 p_3 + K_4 p_4)^5} \quad (\text{E IV})$$

The significance of subscripts are as follows: 1-carbon dioxide, 2-hydrogen; 3-methane; 4-water; index j in eqn. (2) refers to a certain gas denoted by 1, 2, 3 and 4. The entropy variation of one component in the adsorption process is given by the difference of two terms: $\Delta S_j^0 = S_{aj}^0 - S_{gj}^0$; S_{aj}^0 and S_{gj}^0 stand for the standard entropy in adsorbed and gas state, respectively (both in $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$). In the calculations use was made of the entropies in gaseous state S_g^0 of the participants in methanation reaction¹⁴: CO_2 , 213.69; H_2 , 130.61; CH_4 , 186.23; H_2O , 188.79 $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

The rate constant of chemical reaction (k) is

$$k = \exp \left[\frac{\Delta S^0}{R} \right] \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{\Delta E}{RT} \right] \quad (3)$$

In Arrhenius type eqn. (3), ΔS^0 stands for the variation of entropy in (chemical) activation process and E for activation energy of the chemical reaction.

In order that the parameters in eqns. (2) and (3) possess a physical significance they are assigned the following signs:

$$\Delta S^0 \text{-positive; } E \text{-positive} \\ (\text{refers to chemical reaction}); \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta S_j^0 \text{-negative; } \Delta H_j^0 \text{-negative} \\ (\text{refers to adsorption equilibrium})$$

To single out the model whose approximation of the catalytic process real mechanism is best one should check whether Boudart criteria¹⁵ are observed or not; the four criteria evaluate the physical significance of the parameters estimated from a model. The four Boudart criteria (when enthalpies are expressed in J mol^{-1} and entropies in $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and $j \neq 0$) are:

- (i) ΔS_j^0 should be negative
 (ii) $|\Delta S_j^0| < \Delta S_{gj}^0$
 (iii) $|\Delta S_j^0| > 41.85$
 (iv) $-\Delta S_j^0 < 51.057 - 0.0014 \Delta H_j^0$

Boudart criteria were considered in many contributions¹³ as fundamental in the selection of the process mechanism although they were not adequate in all instances.

Establishing the most probable reaction mechanism :

Several methods have been employed in estimating the kinetic parameters of a catalytic process in case the reaction rates take differential or integral form. Sequential (step by step) methods seek the selection of the optimal model from among the possible kinetic models and estimation of optimal kinetic parameters which correspond to optimal model¹⁶.

According to Hill *et al.*¹⁶, there are three kinds of basic methods of optimization by minimizing function F , referred to as objective function : (1) methods that employ F function, (2) gradient methods which make use on function F as well as its partial derivatives with respect to independent variables and (3) Newton type methods which include in the expression of iteration cycle function F and its first and second order derivatives. From the first kind we mention Fletcher-Powell and Fletcher-Reeves methods¹⁶ which seek the solutions for n -dimensional quadratic functions along n conjugated one-dimensional directions.

The effective minimizing of the objective functions of sum of squares type makes use of well known algorithms (Gauss-Newton, Levenberg-Marquardt, Powell etc.), whose efficiency in solving nonlinear problems of parameter estimation has drawn the attention of many authors¹⁷. From among these algorithms Powell's one is a function method (that requires no gradient calculation) which has been very efficient in practice. Therefore, this algorithm was chosen in order to select the optimal kinetic model (supported by experimental data) from among those adequate for the mechanisms of carbon dioxide methanation reaction on the catalyst studied.

In order to make possible the computer processing of kinetic data previously obtained, Table 1 lists only the values of the quantities present in eqns. (E I)-(E IV) of the reaction rates according to mechanisms (I)-(IV). The kinetic measurements were numbered from 1 to 28 in the sequence of the experiments carried out with A-G feed mixtures (four for each experiment).

The problem to be solved, in its most general form, consists of minimization, with restraints, of the objective function F . The form of the objective function originates in the

Table 1. Steady state parameters

Run no.	$r \times 10^3$ mol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹	T K	p_1 atm	p_2 atm	p_3 atm	p_4 atm
1	2.87	524	0.0611	0.7505	0.0309	0.0617
2	4.01	539	0.0501	0.7193	0.0442	0.0883
3	4.92	550	0.0409	0.6930	0.0553	0.1107
4	5.31	555	0.0368	0.6814	0.0603	0.1205
5	2.65	523	0.0707	0.7724	0.0209	0.0419
6	3.88	538	0.0621	0.7479	0.0313	0.0626
7	5.54	556	0.0501	0.7136	0.0459	0.0917
8	6.91	571	0.0396	0.6837	0.0586	0.1171
9	3.30	531	0.0656	0.7824	0.0209	0.0418
10	4.84	550	0.0570	0.7582	0.0312	0.0624
11	6.52	568	0.0471	0.7306	0.0430	0.0860
12	8.29	587	0.0363	0.7004	0.0560	0.1119
13	1.95	516	0.0655	0.8078	0.0152	0.0304
14	3.69	537	0.0533	0.7744	0.0296	0.0592
15	4.61	548	0.0466	0.7559	0.0376	0.0753
16	7.01	575	0.0281	0.7052	0.0595	0.1191
17	3.88	528	0.1204	0.6931	0.0313	0.0626
18	6.02	550	0.1068	0.6465	0.0503	0.1006
19	7.43	565	0.0973	0.6138	0.0636	0.1271
20	8.65	576	0.0888	0.5843	0.0755	0.1511
21	4.99	525	0.1828	0.6072	0.0409	0.0819
22	6.13	539	0.1767	0.5805	0.0513	0.1027
23	7.24	553	0.1706	0.5537	0.0617	0.1234
24	11.83	590	0.1426	0.4309	0.1094	0.2189
25	4.17	537	0.0690	0.6757	0.0539	0.1078
26	5.25	549	0.0565	0.6374	0.0699	0.1399
27	6.29	560	0.0439	0.5989	0.0861	0.1721
28	6.63	564	0.0396	0.5856	0.0916	0.1832

Hougen-Watson type, (E I)-(E IV) expressions. The objective function F is equal to the sum of the squares of differences between calculated and experimental values of reaction rates (as part of a given model),

$$F = \sum_{i=1}^{28} \left[\frac{\prod_{j=0}^m K_{ij}^{n_j} \prod_{j=1}^m p_{ij}^{n_j}}{\left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^s K_{ij} p_{ij}\right)^s} - r_i \right]^2, \quad (6)$$

where K_{ij} represents a convenient alternative of eqn. (2), which takes the expression,

$$K_{ij} = \exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_j^0}{R} \right] \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{\Delta H_j^0}{RT_i} \right] \quad (7)$$

In eqns. (6) and (7), $j = 0$ refers to the chemical reaction, while j from 1 to 4 stands for carbon dioxide, hydrogen, methane and water, respectively. In eqn. (6), $m = 2$, $n_0 = 1$, $n_1 = 2$, $n_2 = 4$, and s takes the value which corresponds to

an analytical writing of eqns. (E I)-(E IV).

The ΔS_j^0 and ΔH_j^0 quantities result from minimization of objective function F ; the partial pressures (p_{ij}) experimental reaction rates (r_i) and absolute temperatures (T_i) are known. The quantities ΔS_j^0 and ΔH_j^0 should obey the conditions (4) and lie within the a priori established ranges of values :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S_0^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}) &\in [30; 120] \\ E = \Delta H_0^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1}) &\in [13000; 105000] \\ \Delta S_j^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}) &\in [-84; -12]; j \neq 0 \\ \Delta H_j^0 (\text{J mol}^{-1}) &\in [-50500; -8300]; j \neq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

The steps of objective function F minimization are presented next.

A limiting condition was accomplished making use of a substitution and the second condition was obeyed by means of a limiting procedure which ensured the continuity of objective function throughout the whole minimum searching domain.

If $\Delta S_j^0 > 0$ in eqn. (7), the following substitution is operated :

$$\exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_j^0}{R} \right] = D_j + x_j^2 \quad (9)$$

and if $\Delta S_j^0 < 0$:

$$\exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_j^0}{R} \right] = \frac{E_j}{1 + x_j^2} \quad (10)$$

The substitutions for enthalpy variations are similar.

In substitutions (9) and (10), D_j and E_j represent one of the two limits required for each ΔS_j^0 and ΔH_j^0 . Because

$$\exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_0^0}{R} \right] \in [D_0, \gamma_0] \quad (11)$$

or

$$\exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_0^0}{R} \right] \in [\delta_j, E_j]; j \neq 0 \quad (12)$$

one gets,

$$\exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_0^0}{R} \right] = D_0 + x_0^2 \leq \gamma_0 \quad (13)$$

or

$$\exp \left[\frac{\Delta S_j^0}{R} \right] = \frac{E_j}{1 + x_j^2} \geq \gamma_j, j \neq 0 \quad (14)$$

and consequently one can consider that

$$|x_0| = \sqrt{\gamma_0 - D_0} \quad (15)$$

or

$$|x_j| = \frac{E_j - \delta_j}{\delta_j}; j \neq 0 \quad (16)$$

(according to the case under study), and for $\exp(\Delta S/R)$, which exceeds the limit, it is readily achieved by means of the program which ensures the continuity of objective function. This approach of the optimization problem mentioned increased the convergence rate of the selected algorithm. In fact, it was practically found out that no satisfactory result was obtained without utilization of the substitutions mentioned.

In order to determine the optimum of the objective function use has been made of a program which utilizes Powell algorithm¹⁶⁻¹⁸ that ensures a quadratic convergence. Thus, if the vector x_0 as initial point, and the nonlinear function $F(x)$ are given (particularly eqn. (6) with substitutions (9) and (10)), a sequence of minimizations yields an approximate solution of the eqn. $F(x) = 0$ or, in other words, a vector x such that $F(x)$ be minimum.

The following notations are introduced :

$x_{k,i} \equiv x$ vector describing k -th iteration and i -th substitution;

$x_0 \in R^n$ -the best approximation of \bar{x} in minimum;

$D(n \times n) \equiv (d_1, \dots, d_n)$ the matrix of directions (initially those of coordinate axes in n -dimensional space).

The algorithm unfolds as follows :

Step 1. Starting from initial point $x_{k,0}$ (at k -th iteration) one reaches point $x_{k,n}$ through n linear successive minimizations along $d_{k,i}$ directions, that is passing successively through the points :

$$x_{k,i} = x_{k,i-1} + \lambda_{k,i} d_{k,i}; i = \overline{1, n},$$

where λ stands for a scalar parameter which should be determined for each iteration and subiteration such that function $F(x_{k,i})$ should be minimized along $d_{k,i}$ direction, passing through $x_{k,i-1}$ point.

Step 2. λ_k (scalar) parameter is determined such that $F[x_{k,n} + \lambda_k(x_{k,n} - x_{k,0})]$ should be minimum; the new point

$$x_{k+1,0} = x_{k,n} + \lambda_k(x_{k,n} - x_{k,0})$$

is determined by means of calculated λ_k .

Step 3. The new set of directions, $d_{k+1,j}$ is determined by means of formulas :

$$d_{k+1,j} = d_{k,i+1}$$

$$d_{k+1,n-1} = d_{k,n}$$

$$d_{k+1,n} = x_{k,n} - x_{k,0}$$

and one returns to step one. The algorithm is discontinued when a sufficient number of steps were effected or else a sufficiently low value of F was obtained. Because at each iteration and subiteration a linear minimization is operated

Table 2. Optimal values and standard deviations of the parameters calculated for (E I)-(E IV) models of reaction rate

Parameter	E I model		E II model		E III model		E IV model	
	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation	Value	Deviation
ΔS^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	86 14	0 29	86 14	0 62	86 19	0 46	86 19	0 70
E (J mol ⁻¹)	57409 18	102 84	102873 11	218 39	57409 18	161 77	102873 11	246 26
ΔS_1^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-42 90	0 92	-42 95	0 62	-42 90	0 46	-62 90	0 70
ΔH_1^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-50118 2	102 84	-38323 09	218 39	-38323 09	161 77	-50118 20	246 26
ΔS_2^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	-43 51	0 29	-43 51	0 62	-43 51	0 46	-43 45	0 70
ΔH_2^0 (J mol ⁻¹)	-50118 2	102 84	-50118 2	218 39	-50118 20	161 77	-50118 2	246 26
ΔS_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)			-83 21	0 62			-83 21	0 70
ΔH_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹)			-19217 54	218 39			19217 54	246 26
ΔS_3^0 (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)					-59 19	0 46	-83 21	0 70
ΔH_4^0 (J mol ⁻¹)					-19217 54	161 77	-19217 54	246 26

along a given direction, the algorithm requires a special subroutine. In this subroutine the objective function is approximated along one direction with a 2nd degree polynomial through a 3-point interpolation¹⁹.

The preliminary estimation of the parameters employed in making up x_0 vector was as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S_0^0 &= 83.7 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}; E = 54405 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \\ \Delta S_1^0 &= -41.85 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}; \Delta H_1^0 = -23017.5 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \\ \Delta S_2^0 &= -41.85 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}; \Delta H_2^0 = -16740 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \quad (17) \\ \Delta S_3^0 &= -41.85 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}; \Delta H_3^0 = -23017.5 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \\ \Delta S_4^0 &= -41.85 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}; \Delta H_4^0 = -16740 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Results and Discussion

Use has been made of the algorithm presented to calculate the optimal values of the parameters of the catalytic process studied for the kinetic models described by the reaction rate eqns. (E I)-(E IV) (Table 2). The same table lists the standard deviations of calculated optimal parameters. Besides the experimental rates, Table 3 also lists the reaction rates calculated by means of models (E I)-(E IV) making use of the optimal parameters obtained (entropies and enthalpies of the process). The reaction rates are expressed in mol h⁻¹ g⁻¹ multiplied by 10³ to make writing simpler. A statistical evaluation of the kinetic models studied can be performed making use of the experimental and calculated rates of reaction. Table 4 lists the minimal value (F_{\min}) of objective function F , the standard deviation (σ_r) and the average relative deviation (ϵ_r) of experimental rates and those calculated by means of the four kinetic models. The value of relative deviation is less than the relative experimental error ($7 \cdot 10^{-2}$, as previously evaluated) which confers consistency to the data obtained for the kinetic models studied.

Table 3. Experimental and calculated reaction rates for (E I)-(E IV) models of reaction rate

Run no	Exptl	E I model	E II model	E III model	E IV model
1	2 87	2 89	2 92	2 90	2 93
2	4 01	3 97	3 90	3 94	3 92
3	4 92	4 86	4 77	4 83	4 79
4	5 31	5 24	4 99	5 11	4 99
5	2 65	2 67	2 72	2 70	2 74
6	3 88	3 91	3 96	3 93	3 97
7	5 54	5 49	5 45	5 47	5 46
8	6 91	6 73	6 65	6 69	6 64
9	3 30	3 33	3 39	3 35	3 40
10	4 84	4 87	4 92	4 90	4 94
11	6 52	6 49	6 46	6 48	6 47
12	8 29	8 16	8 08	8 11	8 08
13	1 95	1 98	2 04	2 02	2 05
14	3 69	3 67	3 64	3 66	3 64
15	4 61	4 57	4 47	4 49	4 46
16	7 01	6 87	6 67	6 71	6 64
17	3 88	3 92	3 94	3 93	3 97
18	6 02	6 09	6 20	6 14	6 27
19	7 43	7 67	7 83	7 74	7 87
20	8 65	8 99	9 22	9 09	9 27
21	4 99	4 87	4 74	4 81	4 71
22	6 13	6 07	5 92	5 99	5 86
23	7 24	7 28	7 32	7 30	7 36
24	11 83	11 72	11 66	11 69	11 62
25	4 17	4 20	4 27	4 23	4 29
26	5 25	5 25	5 25	5 25	5 24
27	6 29	6 23	6 22	6 23	6 10
28	6 63	6 53	6 43	6 52	6 28

Table 4. Statistical evaluation of calculated reaction rates

Kinetic model	$F_{\min} \times 10^6$ mol ² h ⁻² g ⁻²	$\sigma \times 10^4$ mol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹	$\epsilon_r \times 10^2$
E I	0.31	1.06	1.25
E II	1.16	2.03	2.84
E III	0.67	1.55	2.06
E IV	1.51	2.32	3.28

Table 5. Optimum straight line parameters

Parameter	E I model	E II model	E III model	E IV model
a	0.997	0.993	0.994	0.989
$b \times 10^3$	0.003	0.011	0.011	0.027
h^2	0.997	0.990	0.995	0.988
h	0.999	0.995	0.997	0.934
α	44°56'	44°48'	44°50'	44°41'

The agreement between the reaction rates calculated by means of kinetic models and the experimental values was evaluated by calculating the parameters of optimal straight-lines from plots of experimental reaction rates (on abscissa) versus calculated rates (on ordinate). The slopes (a) and ordinates at origin (b) of optimal lines, the correlation factors (h^2) and correlations (h) as well as the angles between the optimal straight lines (a) and the abscissa are all listed in Table 5. The value close to unit of h correlation points to a good agreement of calculated and experimental reaction rates. The optimal straight-lines whose slopes are close to each other are also very close to the first bisector. To select the real mechanism from among those proposed the results

obtained were analyzed (Table 6) by means of Boudart criteria (5). Whenever a criterion is not verified the symbol NV appears in the table.

Boudart criteria are fully valid in case of the values obtained with the equations of reaction rates (E I) and (E III). Eqn. (E I) was thought under the hypothesis that carbon dioxide and hydrogen react in adsorbed state while methane and water show up in the gaseous state of the process. Eqn. (E III) assumes that following the process which occurs among the adsorbed reactants only methane is in gas phase, while water resulted from the process is adsorbed on catalyst surface.

While the activation energies of the catalytic process and the (chemical) activation entropies of eqns. (E I) and (E III) coincide (Table 2), the rather small adsorption enthalpy of water suggests its weak adsorption on catalyst surface. Therefore, the actual mechanism of carbon dioxide methanation reaction on the catalyst studied is mechanism (I) without marked tendency to approach mechanism (III).

Rouleau *et al.*¹³ applied the same method in a study on the actual mechanism of carbon dioxide methanation with Ru/Al₂O₃ catalyst; they considered mechanism (I) as the real mechanism and obtained the activation energy and entropy variation in the process 57574.3 J mol⁻¹ and 86.67 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively. These values are practically identical to those obtained in the present contribution: $E = 57409$ J mol⁻¹ and $\Delta S_0^0 = 86$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹.

The results obtained in this contribution for the two

Table 6. Boudart criteria (BC) applied to the results

Model	BC	CO ₂	H ₂	CH ₄	H ₂ O
E I	(i)	-42.90	-43.51		
	(ii)	42.90 < 213.69	43.51 < 130.61		
	(iii)	42.90 > 41.85	43.51 > 41.85		
	(iv)	42.90 < 121.22	43.51 < 121.22		
E II	(i)	-42.95	-43.51	-83.21	
	(ii)	42.95 < 213.69	43.51 < 130.61	83.21 < 186.23	
	(iii)	42.95 > 41.85	43.51 > 41.85	83.21 > 41.85	
	(iv)	42.95 < 104.71	43.51 < 121.22	83.21 > 77.96 NV	
E III	(i)	-42.90	-43.51		-59.19
	(ii)	42.90 < 213.69	43.51 < 130.61		59.19 < 188.79
	(iii)	42.90 > 41.85	43.51 > 41.85		59.19 > 41.85
	(iv)	42.90 < 104.71	43.51 < 121.22		59.19 < 77.96
E IV	(i)	-42.90	-43.45	-83.21	-83.21
	(ii)	42.90 < 213.69	43.45 < 130.61	83.21 < 186.23	83.21 < 188.79
	(iii)	42.90 > 41.85	43.45 > 41.85	83.21 > 41.85	83.21 > 41.85
	(iv)	42.90 < 121.22	43.45 < 121.22	83.21 > 77.96 NV	83.21 > 77.96 NV

mechanisms, (I) and (III) of Langmuir and Hinshelwood type, justify Rouleau's neglecting the adsorption of water. These results also agree to those of Binder and White²⁰, van Herwijnen *et al.*²¹ and Amariglio *et al.*²² who studied the methanation of carbon dioxide on nickel catalyst. Lunde and Kester²³ studied the same reaction on ruthenium catalyst. Although no attempt was made to determine the reaction mechanism, the activation energy of the process was determined by means of an empirical correlation; it amounts to 70455.4 J mol⁻¹.

Conclusions : The kinetic data of CO₂ methanation reaction on Ni/Al₂O₃ catalyst were analyzed by means of four possible mechanisms of the process based on the adsorption of molecular species on catalyst surface. These models are described by Hougen-Watson type reaction rate equations. The kinetic parameters from the reaction rate equations were obtained by minimizing the sum of squared residuals making use of the modified Powell's algorithm. Selecting the mechanism process from the possible ones, was carried out by means of Boudart criteria. It was established that methanation of CO₂ on the catalyst studied occurs according to a Langmuir-Hinshelwood mechanism; the reaction occurs between carbon dioxide and hydrogen both adsorbed on catalyst surface, while methane and water result from the process in gaseous phase.

Experimental

Catalyst preparation : The methanation catalyst was obtained by coprecipitation of aluminium hydroxide and nickel basic carbonate from a solution of nickel and aluminium nitrates with ammonium carbonate²⁴. Before activation, the catalyst contained 20.23 NiO, 55 Al₂O₃, 8.6 CaO, 14.17 H₂O and 2% graphite; it was shaped as cylindrical tablets (6 mm in dia and 7 mm height).

Catalyst characterisation : Use was made of mercury penetration porosimetry (porosimeter Carlo-Erba 70H) to determine the apparent density (2.124 g cm⁻³), pore volume (0.204 cm³ g⁻¹) and surface area (89 m² g⁻¹). Most of the pore radii (over 60% of the overall pore volume) range within 37.5–150 Å, therefore internal diffusion entails important limitations of reaction rate which can be diminished by grinding the catalyst at 1.25–1.60 mm. The average mechanical axial strength and average mechanical radial strength were 170 kgf cm⁻² and 35 kgf cm⁻¹, respectively (Wolpert ZR 60/300).

The X-rays analysis (diffractometer Philips PW1140) of the unreduced methanation catalyst evidenced NiO phase of intermediate crystallinity (about 140 Å) on hydrated alumina support consisting of γ -AlOOH (boehmite) and α -

Al(OH)₃ (gibbsite or hydrargilite), the former being less dispersed than the latter. Very small amounts of CaAl₂O₄ and Ca₂Fe₂O₅ were also identified. Following reduction, at least 60% of NiO transformed into metallic Ni in advanced state of dispersion (about 60 Å). Regarding the support, the reduction entailed the decomposition of gibbsite which turned into boehmite and θ -alumina; small amounts of CaAlO₄, CaAl₄O₇, Ca₃Al₂O₆ and Ca₂Fe₂O₅ accompanied the mentioned compounds.

Electron diffraction on unreduced sample showed that nickel oxide is very weakly crystallized. Regarding the morphologic aspect of unreduced sample nickel and aluminium oxides were not separated. Nickel oxide was present as fine particles, usually smaller than 200 Å, which sometimes agglomerated in granules of 2000 Å or even larger. When nickel oxide was dispersed, the pore size was of the same order of magnitude as particle size or smaller. The most frequent porosity of alumina support lied in the range of very small pores (below 50 Å). The electron diffraction also showed that after catalyst reduction nickel oxide transformed partially into metallic nickel whose pores were very fine (less than 100 Å) and formed spongy agglomerations whose pores were of the order of magnitude of crystallites. In this case the support was also weakly crystallized. The

Table 7. Composition of gas mixtures used for reactor feed (given in normal conditions of temperature and pressure)

Gas mixture	Total dm ³ h ⁻¹	Gas	Comp. %	Flow dm ³ h ⁻¹	Flow × 10 ³ mol h ⁻¹
A	7.5	H ₂	82.32	6.17	254.96
		N ₂	9.02	0.68	27.94
		CO ₂	8.66	0.65	26.82
B	10	H ₂	82.17	8.22	339.32
		N ₂	9.04	0.90	37.33
		CO ₂	8.79	0.88	36.30
C	12.5	H ₂	83.12	10.39	429.06
		N ₂	8.58	1.07	44.29
		CO ₂	8.30	1.04	42.84
D	10	H ₂	84.30	8.43	348.12
		N ₂	7.87	0.79	32.50
		CO ₂	7.83	0.78	32.33
E	10	H ₂	77.01	7.70	318.02
		N ₂	8.72	0.87	35.99
		CO ₂	14.27	1.43	58.94
F	10	H ₂	71.26	7.12	294.28
		N ₂	8.06	0.81	33.28
		CO ₂	20.68	2.07	85.39
G	6.5	H ₂	80.46	5.23	215.97
		N ₂	8.45	0.55	22.68
		CO ₂	11.09	0.72	29.77

Table 8. Composition of gases after the reaction and the reaction rates

Run no	Temp. K	Composition %					Flow $\times 10^3$ mol h ⁻¹					Reaction rate $\times 10^3$ mol h ⁻¹ g ⁻¹
		H ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	CO ₂	H ₂ O	H ₂	N ₂	CH ₄	CO ₂	H ₂ O	
Mixture A feed (7.5 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
1	524	75.05	9.58	3.09	6.11	6.17	218.94	37.94	9.00	17.82	18.01	2.87
2	539	71.93	9.82	4.42	5.01	8.83	204.70	27.94	12.56	14.26	25.13	4.01
3	550	69.30	10.02	5.53	4.09	11.07	193.25	27.94	15.43	11.39	30.85	4.92
4	555	68.14	10.11	6.03	3.68	12.05	188.35	27.94	16.65	10.17	33.30	5.31
Mixture B feed (10 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
5	523	77.24	9.42	2.09	7.07	4.19	306.13	37.33	8.30	28.00	16.59	2.65
6	538	74.79	9.61	3.13	6.21	6.26	290.65	37.33	12.17	24.13	24.33	3.88
7	556	71.36	9.87	4.59	5.01	9.17	269.92	37.33	17.35	18.95	34.70	5.54
8	571	68.37	10.10	5.86	3.96	11.71	252.73	37.33	21.65	14.65	43.29	6.91
Mixture C feed (12.5 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
9	531	78.24	8.94	2.09	6.56	4.18	387.67	44.29	10.35	32.50	20.69	3.30
10	550	75.82	9.12	3.12	5.70	6.24	368.38	44.29	15.17	27.68	30.34	4.84
11	568	73.06	9.32	4.30	4.71	8.60	347.27	44.29	20.45	22.40	40.89	6.52
12	587	70.04	9.54	5.50	3.63	11.19	325.13	44.29	25.98	16.86	51.96	8.29
Mixture D feed (10 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
13	516	80.78	8.11	1.52	6.55	3.04	323.72	32.50	6.10	26.23	12.20	1.95
14	537	77.44	8.34	2.96	5.33	5.93	301.91	32.50	11.55	20.78	23.10	3.69
15	548	75.59	8.46	3.76	4.66	7.53	290.32	32.50	14.45	17.89	28.90	4.61
16	575	70.52	8.81	5.95	2.81	11.91	260.24	32.50	21.97	10.36	43.94	7.01
Mixture E feed (10 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
17	528	69.31	9.26	3.13	12.04	6.26	269.36	35.99	12.17	46.77	24.33	3.88
18	550	64.64	9.59	5.03	10.68	10.06	242.56	35.99	18.87	40.07	37.73	6.02
19	565	61.38	9.82	6.36	9.73	12.71	224.88	35.99	23.29	35.65	46.57	7.43
20	576	58.43	10.03	7.55	8.88	15.11	209.63	35.99	27.10	31.84	54.20	8.65
Mixture F feed (10 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
21	525	60.72	8.72	4.09	18.28	8.19	231.77	33.28	15.63	69.76	31.26	4.99
22	539	58.07	8.89	5.13	17.68	10.27	217.39	33.28	19.22	66.17	38.45	6.13
23	553	55.37	9.06	6.17	17.06	12.34	203.54	33.28	22.68	62.70	45.37	7.24
24	590	43.09	9.82	10.94	14.26	21.89	145.97	33.28	37.08	48.31	74.15	11.83
Mixture G feed (6.5 dm ³ h ⁻¹):												
25	537	67.57	9.36	5.39	6.90	10.78	163.72	22.68	13.06	16.70	26.13	4.17
26	549	63.74	9.63	6.99	5.65	13.99	150.10	22.68	16.47	13.30	32.93	5.25
27	560	59.89	9.90	8.61	4.39	17.21	137.15	22.68	19.71	10.06	39.41	6.29
28	564	58.56	9.99	9.16	3.96	18.33	132.84	22.68	20.79	8.98	41.56	6.63

morphologic aspect of reduced sample did not differ significantly from that of unreduced sample. The catalytic properties of the surface, related directly to the structure of the catalyst, were determined by its ability to form bonds with the molecules in gaseous phase. Therefore, in order to develop an image of the state of electrons in the catalyst and on its surface, studies of electric conductivity and Seebeck effect were carried out on the methanation catalyst²⁵.

Kinetic study : The kinetic study of carbon dioxide methanation process on the catalyst described was carried

out in a perfectly stirred reactor⁶. The catalyst (4 cm³, 3.134 g, 1.25–1.60 mm size) was introduced in the reactor. It was activated by reduction with hydrogen for 12 h at 673 K. The temperature was then lowered to 423 K and carbon dioxide was progressively introduced. The rotation speed of the stirrer was maintained at 2600 rpm throughout the catalyst reduction (activation) and during kinetic measurements because this speed ensured perfect mixing⁶.

To use of kinetic data in obtaining the kinetic parameters (and kinetic equation) the activity tests were effected in ki-

netic reaction conditions over a wide range of carbon dioxide content (7.83–20.68 % vol). Seven experiments were carried out in kinetic conditions with various compositions of feed gas mixtures (denoted from A to G, Table 7) and at four different reaction temperatures (gas chromatograph Fisons Instruments 8000). Table 8 lists the composition of gases after the reaction and the reaction rates expressed in moles of CO₂ transformed in one hour per gram of catalyst. The results of replica measurements showed that at temperatures above 515 K, the relative experimental error of reaction rates reached a maximum of 7.10^{-2} .

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